

Tårup Dark Sky Festival

Sted: Tårup, Kunstrum Fyn.

Tid: 31. august 2023 – 03. september 2023.

URL: <https://www.kunstrumfyn.dk/about-trup-dark-sky>

To
Tobias C. Hinse

From
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Certification document

Hereby Kunstrum Fyn certifies that Tobias C. Hinse partially organized and contributed to the 2023 Tårup Dark Sky Festival (<https://www.kunstrumfyn.dk/about-trup-dark-sky>) during the period 31. August to 2. September 2023.

Tobias' main contribution was science outreach and communication to festival visitors (children and adults) with focus on astronomy, astrophysics and the problem of artificial light pollution and the involvement of Citizen Science.

Yours truly

A handwritten signature in black ink, appearing to read "Helga-Marie Nordby".

Helga-Marie Nordby
Chair, Kunstrum Fyn

Tårup, 6 September 2023